

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report will summarize the evaluation of top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiation balance against observations, and tests of sensitivity of the radiation budget to variations in processes affecting it.

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WP4

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1 Executive summary

Climate models are often used to conduct climate change experiments in response to external forcings such as carbon dioxide increases. In order to do so it is necessary that the models can also maintain a stationary climate if no such forcing is applied. This requires an energy balance between sources and sinks, ideally between the incoming solar radiation and the reflected and emitted radiation at the top of the atmosphere. This balance is highly sensitive to even small changes in cloudiness. Also numerical model imperfections can cause artificial sources or sinks of energy, which must be compensated for in order to obtain a stationary basic climate. We provide successful examples and conclude that obtaining radiation balance and a stable climate in the nextGEMS models is challenging but clearly feasible.

2 Conclusion & Results

The finished work described here shows that stabilising the top of atmosphere radiation balance is feasible in the nextGEMS models. If combined with the small energy leakage levels achieved in the IFS model a stationary climate can be attained. Alternatively, if the energy leakage is known as in the ICON model, the radiation balance can be used to compensate. This technique is less desirable, but practical until the energy leakages have been remedied.

Relative to contemporary climate models we find that the radiation balance appears to be relatively good in the nextGEMS models already before parameter tuning has been conducted. This makes it easier to attain radiation balance since fewer parameters must be changed. Also, since the anticipated model runs are relatively short, the requirements on accurate tuning are lower than for contemporary climate models that are typically spun up and run for thousands of years. For example the spin-up of MPI-ESM1.2-LR was 10,000 years. We further find that short runs of about 5 days, before chaos takes over, can be informative of the effect of tuning parameters, which alleviates some of the high computational cost of running the nextGEMS models. Nevertheless, the computational cost and time required to run these simulations remains challenging.

All in all, we conclude that attaining radiation balance is feasible, and that a stable climate can be obtained if the model energy leakage is known. Nevertheless, the presence of energy leakage can be problematic for other reasons, for example it may affect the circulation. Moving forward we therefore recommend that energy leakages in the nextGEMS models are monitored, and if possible remedied.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	yes
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	yes
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O3	
To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:	
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	no

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP4	Relevance in this deliverable?
To stabilize the climate of next-generation models by balancing top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiation and implement a simplified aerosol scheme, in order to enable studies of Earth's climate sensitivity and aerosol forcing in the Application phase (WP5). (O1)	yes
To identify shortcomings related to remaining sub-grid scale processes, including representation of turbulent transport and mixing, cloud microphysics and subgrid cloud structures. (O1)	yes
To implement online diagnostics of wind energy potential in an innovative bi-directional endeavour, jointly with stakeholders, in order to prepare an assessment of the impacts of changing emissions of CO2 and aerosols on efforts to replace fossil fuels with renewable energy in the Application phase. (O3)	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

The planetary radiation imbalance, the difference between incoming 340 Wm^{-2} of Sunlight and the reflected and emitted terrestrial radiation, is long recognised as the control on global climate change (Arrhenius, 1896; Forster et al., 2021). The imbalance is defined at the top of the atmosphere (TOA). The current best estimate is that the imbalance is $0.87 \pm 0.12 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ over the period 2010-2018 (von Schuckmann et al., 2020). This relatively small imbalance of less than 0.3 percent leads to the accumulation of energy in the Earth's climate system which results in the ongoing global warming with many consequences around the globe.

In global climate models, both contemporary and those of the next generation, radiation imbalance plays an additional role in controlling model drifts. Since both these categories of models are imperfect foremost in their representation of clouds and their ability to conserve energy, even small errors can lead to substantial artificial drifts at rates that are scientifically prohibitive away from the climate they are intended to represent, for example the near-stationary pre-industrial climate or the present. Energy conservation is often violated in climate models, either due to programming errors or formulations that inherently do not conserve energy. These can act as artificial energy sources or leaks and must be compensated by errors of opposite sign in the radiation balance to achieve a stationary climate (Mauritsen et al., 2012). What is prohibitive depends on the length of the simulations that are desired, whereas contemporary climate models are typically run for a thousand years or more, currently the next generation storm resolving models are run for years of multiple decades. Therefore in the latter case larger imperfections can be tolerated, although demands will certainly increase towards the end of the nextGEMS project.

The radiation balance is usually controlled by adjusting, or tuning, various model parameters that can affect the radiation balance (Mauritsen et al., 2012). Also many other aspects of the model's behavior can be factored in, and the strategies of model tuning varies between institutes (Hourdin et al., 2017; Mauritsen and Roeckner, 2020). The parameters that are tuned are typically related to clouds, for example controlling cloud amount, their distribution or optical depth, but there are also examples of using the ocean surface reflectivity (albedo) to compensate for a lack of low-level clouds. Below we detail experience and results obtained for the nextGEMS models.

Experience from ICON-Sapphire

The development and tuning of the radiation balance went hand in hand in the early developments of the ICON-Sapphire model, and the resulting experience is extensively documented (Mauritsen et al., 2022; Hohenegger et al., 2023); here shortly summarised. Numerous runs were conducted in the early stages of the model development, both to improve the numerical stability and ability to run at high throughputs, but also to evaluate the realism and stability of the model climate. The first multi-month run (dpp0001) exhibited a surprisingly realistic global mean temperature, but at a radiation balance approximately 5 Wm^{-2} above the observed (Fig. 1). Later simulations, such as dpp0029/33, had more realistically tuned radiation balance but at the expense of a gradually cooling global temperature.

Two additional simulations cast light on this finding. These were decade long simulations conducted with a slightly lower resolution of 10 km (Fig. 2). Here we combine the temperature and radiation imbalance in one plot, and displayed in orange is the observed cycle. The 8-shaped curve is the result of a finite effective heat capacity. With the at the time standard setup with the Smagorinski turbulent mixing scheme (ngc2012) the model would start with about 10 Wm^{-2}

Figure 1: Evolution of temperature and radiation balance with time in the coupled simulations. Left panel shows daily global mean temperature in simulations compared with the average annual cycle from HadCRUT 5.0 global temperature reconstruction averaged over the 2001-2020 period (Morice et al., 2021). Starting dates of the experiments are marked with vertical dashed lines. The right panel shows the top of atmosphere radiation balance compared to monthly mean observed radiation balance from CERES-EBAF edition 4.1 (Loeb et al., 2018) averaged over the 2001-2020 period. Note that the right panel only shows the first year of dpp0029/33, and also that dpp0005 has quadrupled CO₂ and so is therefore not expected to match observations.

Figure 2: Two 10 year long simulations with ICON-Sapphire at 10 km resolution, as well as observations that are also shown in Figure 1. The ngc2012 simulation drifts to colder temperatures with time, whereas the ngc2013 simulation exhibits a stable climate over several decades.

Figure 3: Comparison of infrared brightness temperature observed from the Seviri weather satellite (a), with 12-hour initialised runs from an early version of ICON-Sapphire with diagnostic cloud micro physics (b), and with the numerical weather prediction (NWP) physics package that includes prognostic cloud micro physics used by the German Weather Service (DWD) (c).

lower radiation balance than observed and then drift rapidly to colder temperatures. This negative radiation balance is the result of too abundant low-level clouds.

The other run with the TTE turbulent mixing scheme (ngc2013) would start with a more positive radiation imbalance approximately 5 Wm^{-2} above the observed as result of too few clouds. However, the temperature in this run did not drift warmer, rather it is roughly stationary near the observed temperature. Further analysis showed that this is due to an energy leakage in the ICON-Sapphire model of approximately 5 Wm^{-2} : the extra input of energy from the radiation imbalance is leaked out of the model rather than being accumulated. This is a common problem in global climate models (Mauritsen et al., 2012), and usually compensated for by tuning the radiation balance so as to have compensating errors.

In addition to the global mean observations and long term drifts, also short runs initialised from analysed states of the atmosphere were informative for the development and tuning of the ICON-Sapphire model. Figure 3 shows a comparison between a high resolution satellite image of outgoing longwave radiation diagnosed from multiple Seviri channels compared with two versions of the ICON model. First, the strong resemblance reveals the strength of these initialised runs as individual modelled clouds can be directly compared with those observed. Also, we note that the observed clouds are visually larger and more organised than those in the model.

Furthermore, these short initialised simulations, akin to a weather forecast, turned out to be useful beyond the visual impressions described above. These short runs of about 5 days of length could also be used for quantitative tuning (Mauritsen et al., 2022). This is because on such time scale roughly the same weather events occur, and changes to the fast model physics parameterisations affect their radiative effect in ways which turned out to be highly correlated with the long term response of the radiation balance. This way, the sensitivity of the model to tuning parameters can be explored with relatively inexpensive runs and this makes it possible to tune the model within reasonable real time.

Experience from IFS

Figure 4: Daily mean water non-conservation (left) and daily mean atmospheric energy imbalance (right), as a function of lead time for IFS nextGEMS Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 simulations. Water non-conservation is computed as the daily change in globally integrated total water, taking account of surface evaporation and precipitation, as a fraction of the daily precipitation.

Thanks to feedback from the hackathons and work within nextGEMS as well as parallel developments at ECMWF, the IFS-NEMO/FESOM model that is used for the nextGEMS simulations has significantly evolved. At the first nextGEMS hackathon, strong water and energy imbalances were identified in the IFS Cycle 1 simulations. More specifically, an artificial source of water was identified, responsible for 4.6% of total precipitation in the simulation with deep convection parametrization at 9 km, and for 10.7% without deep convection parametrization at 4.5 km, as well as for an atmospheric energy imbalance of 2.0 W m^{-2} at 9 km, and of 6.4 W m^{-2} at 4.5 km resolution (Figure 4).

Thanks to these hackathon results, a model setup was developed by nextGEMS and ECMWF model development teams in which water vapour, cloud liquid, cloud ice, rain and snow are conserved globally. With these global mass fixers, global water non-conservation was essentially eliminated (about 0.1%) in the nextGEMS Cycle 2 simulations, while the global atmospheric energy budget imbalance reduced to less than 1 W m^{-2} (Figure 4).

With the problem of atmospheric energy imbalance mostly solved, the focus of IFS model development was then on the global top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiation imbalance. Relative to CERES observations, IFS simulations for nextGEMS Cycle 2 showed less of an overestimation of outgoing longwave radiation relative to Cycle 1, reducing the TOA longwave bias. However, the TOA shortwave bias got worse. There was not enough shortwave radiation reflected to begin with, and this bias increased because of the fixes introduced to improve water conservation. In total, the TOA net imbalance worsened and was, relative to CERES, about $+2 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ in Cycle 2 (Figure 5). Due to this TOA imbalance, the nextGEMS Cycle 2 simulations warmed too much, by 1–2 K over the course of one year (Figure 6). Thus, addressing the TOA radiation imbalance was a major development focus in preparation for the longer time integrations planned for nextGEMS Cycle 3.

In nextGEMS Cycle 3 we will use a combination of model changes targeting to reduce the TOA radiation imbalance, mostly affecting cloud amount. These include: (i) a change restricting the detrainment of mid-level convection to the liquid phase in most situations, (ii) a decrease of a threshold that limits the minimum size of ice effective radius, in agreement with observational evidence, (iii) an adaptation of cloud edge erosion, reducing the general rate of cloud edge erosion but increasing cloud edge erosion when cloud fraction is very small or almost 1. The latter

Figure 5: Global-mean longwave (top), shortwave (mid) and net (bottom) TOA radiation bias in Cycle 2 and Cycle 3 prototype simulations, relative to CERES-EBAF 2001-2021 climatology of monthly means. The grey area shows the range of monthly CERES observations relative to the long-term mean and therefore indicates the range of internal variability.

Figure 6: Global-mean monthly 2m temperature (GSAT) in Cycle 2 and Cycle 3 prototype simulations, in comparison to the 2013-2022 ERA 5 climatology of monthly mean, with the standard deviation in shading.

is done by assuming a fixed effective cloud spacing rather than a fixed effective cloud scale, which is in closer agreement with observations (Fielding et al., 2020); (iv) a reduction of the cloud inhomogeneity, which increases cloud amount as it reduces the rate of accretion. This change is in line with nextGEMS's km-scale resolutions as cloud inhomogeneity is expected to be smaller at high resolutions; (v) in agreement with nextGEMS Cycle 2 but unlike in the operational IFS, linear rather than cubic interpolation is used for the departure point interpolation of the Semi-Lagrangian advection scheme for all moist species except water vapour; (vi) a modification of the microphysics for rain and snow evaporation. Instead of using an artificial threshold on relative humidity that prohibits evaporation when relative humidity is above 80%, a sub-grid relative humidity enhancement scheme has been introduced, following the top-hat assumption of Tiedtke (1993), precipitation fraction is reduced proportionally when rain evaporates, and the general rate of rain evaporation has been reduced.

A first 1-year prototype IFS simulation for nextGEMS Cycle 3 at 9 km resolution with these model changes targeting the TOA radiation imbalance showed that the net TOA radiation imbalance is indeed reduced to -0.3 W m^{-2} , with a shortwave bias of 0.7 W m^{-2} and a longwave bias of -1 W m^{-2} relative to the CERES EBAF 2001-2021 multi-year average (Figure 5). As a result, the global mean 2m temperature is in the Cycle 3 prototype simulation in close agreement with ERA 5, averaged over 2017–2021, unlike the Cycle 2 simulations which all show a substantial warming (Figure 6).

References

- Arrhenius, S.A. On the Influence of Carbonic Acid in the Air upon the Temperature of the Ground. *Philosophical Magazine*, 41, 237-276, 1896.
- Fielding, M.D., S.A.K. Schäfer, R.J. Hogan, and R.M. Forbes, 2020: Parametrizing cloud geometry and its application in a subgrid cloud-edge erosion scheme. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, 146, 1651–1667, <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3758>
- Forster, P., T. Storelvmo, K. Armour, W. Collins, J.-L. Dufresne, D. Frame, D.J. Lunt, T. Mauritsen, M.D. Palmer, M. Watanabe, M. Wild, and H. Zhang, 2021: The Earth's Energy Budget, Climate Feedbacks, and Climate Sensitivity. In *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 923–1054, doi:10.1017/9781009157896.009.
- Hohenegger, C., Korn, P., Linardakis, L., Redler, R., Schnur, R., Adamidis, P., Bao, J., Bastin, S., Behraves, M., Bergemann, M., Biercamp, J., Bockelmann, H., Brokopf, R., Brüggemann, N., Casaroli, L., Chegini, F., Datseris, G., Esch, M., George, G., Giorgetta, M., Gutjahr, O., Haak, H., Hanke, M., Ilyina, T., Jahns, T., Jungclaus, J., Kern, M., Klocke, D., Kluft, L., Kölling, T., Kornblueh, L., Kosukhin, S., Kroll, C., Lee, J., Mauritsen, T., Mehlmann, C., Mieslinger, T., Naumann, A. K., Paccini, L., Peinado, A., Praturi, D. S., Putrasahan, D., Rast, S., Riddick, T., Roeber, N., Schmidt, H., Schulzweida, U., Schütte, F., Segura, H., Shevchenko, R., Singh, V., Specht, M., Stephan, C. C., von Storch, J.-S., Vogel, R., Wengel, C., Winkler, M., Ziemann, F., Marotzke, J., and Stevens, B.: ICON-Sapphire: simulating the components of the Earth system and their interactions at kilometer and subkilometer scales, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 16, 779–811, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-779-2023>, 2023.
- Hourdin, F., Mauritsen, T., Gettelman, A., Golaz, J., Balaji, V., Duan, Q., Folini, D., Ji, D., Klocke,

D., Qian, Y., Rauser, F., Rio, C., Tomassini, L., Watanabe, M., and Williamson, D. 2017. The Art and Science of Climate Model Tuning, *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 98(3), 589–602.

Loeb, N. G., D. R. Doelling, H. Wang, W. Su, C. Nguyen, J. G. Corbett, L. Liang, C. Mitrescu, F. G. Rose, and S. Kato, 2018. Clouds and the Earth’s Radiant Energy System (CERES) Energy Balanced and Filled (EBAF) Top-of-Atmosphere (TOA) Edition-4.0 Data Product. *J. Climate*, 31, 895-918, doi: 10.1175/JCLI-D-17-0208.1.

Mauritsen, T., et al. 2012. Tuning the climate of a global model, *J. Adv. Model. Earth Syst.*, 4, M00A01, doi:10.1029/2012MS000154.

Mauritsen, T., and Roeckner, E. 2020. Tuning the MPI-ESM1.2 global climate model to improve the match with instrumental record warming by lowering its climate sensitivity. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 12, e2019MS002037, doi:10.1029/2019MS002037.

Mauritsen, T., Redler, R., Esch, M., Stevens, B., Hohenegger, C., Klocke, D., ... Schnur, R. (2022). Early Development and Tuning of a Global Coupled Cloud Resolving Model, and its Fast Response to Increasing CO₂. *Tellus A: Dynamic Meteorology and Oceanography*, 74(1), 346–363, doi:10.16993/tellusa.54.

Morice, C.P., Kennedy, J.J., Rayner, N.A., Winn, J.P., Hogan, E., Killick, R.E., Dunn, R.J.H., Osborn, T.J., Jones, P.D., and Simpson, I.R. 2021. An updated assessment of near-surface temperature change from 1850: the HadCRUT5 dataset. *Journal of Geophysical Research*. doi:10.1029/2019JD032361.

Tiedtke, M. 1993. Representation of Clouds in Large-Scale Models. *Monthly Weather Review*, 121, 11, 3040-3061. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1993\)121<3040:ROCILS>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1993)121<3040:ROCILS>2.0.CO;2).

von Schuckmann, K., Cheng, L., Palmer, M. D., Hansen, J., Tassone, C., Aich, V., Adusumilli, S., Beltrami, H., Boyer, T., Cuesta-Valero, F. J., Desbruyères, D., Domingues, C., García-García, A., Gentine, P., Gilson, J., Gorfer, M., Haimberger, L., Ishii, M., Johnson, G. C., Killick, R., King, B. A., Kirchengast, G., Kolodziejczyk, N., Lyman, J., Marzeion, B., Mayer, M., Monier, M., Monselesan, D. P., Purkey, S., Roemmich, D., Schweiger, A., Seneviratne, S. I., Shepherd, A., Slater, D. A., Steiner, A. K., Straneo, F., Timmermans, M.-L., and Wijffels, S. E.: Heat stored in the Earth system: where does the energy go?, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 12, 2013–2041, doi:10.5194/essd-12-2013-2020, 2020.

5 Dissemination and uptake

5.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
x	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)

	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

5.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

This document will be freely available to the general public from the project website.

6 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

7 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

8 Sustainability

8.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This deliverable contributes to O1 under A1 and is linked to the WP4 deliverable D4.4 (Report on Cycle 2 hackathon) as part of the analyses done for this task has been achieved during the cycle 2 hackathon.

9 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19.10. – 22.10.2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 1.4. - 3.4.2022 near Madrid

- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26.06. - 02.07. in Vienna
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023

10 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>